

UDC 351.84:364

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International Experience of Volunteering

У статті розглянуто зарубіжний досвід волонтерської діяльності та охарактеризовано сучасне становище українського волонтерства в умовах зовнішньої агресії. Волонтерська діяльність є основою побудови та розвитку громадянського суспільства. Світове співтовариство визнає волонтерський рух способом збереження та зміцнення загальнолюдських цінностей, реалізації прав і обов'язків громадян, особистісного зростання шляхом усвідомлення людського потенціалу.

Метою статті є ґрунтовне дослідження історичного розвитку, стану і статусу волонтерського руху у світі.

Аналіз волонтерського руху зарубіжних країн доводить, що гнучкі форми волонтерської діяльності на практиці виявляються найбільш продуктивними, адже обхід бюрократичних процедур за екстраординарних обставин призводить до економії часу та вреїті-реїт рятує людські життя.

Визначено, що волонтерська робота зарубіжних країн, спрямована на підвищення добробуту суспільства, має свої напрями й форми роботи, які доцільно практично реалізовувати в нашій державі. Звичайно, далеко не всі їхні напрацювання можуть бути застосовні в нас через значні розбіжності, зокрема в соціально-економічному рівні. Разом із тим, взаємозбагачення ідеями й досвідом організації волонтерської роботи — важливий чинник її розвитку в Україні.

Ключові слова: підтримка, волонтерська діяльність, міжнародний досвід, волонтер, допомога.

The article examines the foreign experience of volunteering and characterizes the current situation of Ukrainian volunteering in conditions of external aggression. Volunteer activity is the basis of the construction and development of civil society. The world community recognizes the volunteer movement as a way of preserving and strengthening universal human values, realizing the rights and responsibilities of citizens, and personal growth by realizing human potential. The Universal Declaration of Volunteering states that volunteering is the foundation of civil society, bringing into people's lives the need for peace, freedom, security and justice. The importance of volunteer activity in the global dimension is confirmed by its recognition by the United Nations as a socially beneficial activity on a voluntary basis, which should be an important component of any strategy, aimed at solving problems, especially in such areas as the fight against poverty, sustainable development, health care, disaster prevention and early response, social integration, overcoming social inequality and discrimination, etc.

The purpose of the article is a thorough study of the historical development, state and status of the volunteer movement in the world.

The analysis of the volunteer movement of foreign countries proves that flexible forms of volunteer activity in practice are the most productive, because bypassing bureaucratic procedures under extraordinary circumstances leads to saving time and ultimately saves human lives.

It was determined that the volunteer work of foreign countries, aimed at improving the welfare of society, has its own directions and forms of work, which are expedient to practically implement in our country. Of course, not all of their findings can be applied in our country due to significant differences, in particular at the socio-economic level. At the same time, mutual enrichment with ideas and experience of organizing volunteer work is an important factor in its development in Ukraine.

Keywords: support, volunteering, international experience, volunteer, help.

Statement of the problem. One of the important features of our time is the development of the

volunteer movement, which involves citizens to participate in changing all spheres of life for the better,

forming new relationships in society, which will generally contribute to the solution of today's problems. Volunteer activity is the basis of the construction and development of civil society. It embodies the noblest aspirations of mankind - the desire for peace, freedom, security and justice for all people. The world community recognizes the volunteer movement as a way of preserving and strengthening universal human values, realizing the rights and responsibilities of citizens, and personal growth by realizing human potential. The Universal Declaration of Volunteering states that volunteering is the foundation of civil society, bringing into people's lives the need for peace, freedom, security and justice. The importance of volunteering in the global dimension is confirmed by its recognition by the United Nations as a socially beneficial activity on a voluntary basis, which should be an important component of any strategy aimed at solving problems, especially in such areas as the fight against poverty, sustainable development, health care, disaster prevention and early response, social integration, overcoming social inequality and discrimination, etc. The relevant provisions of the UN Resolution and the recommendation on supporting the volunteer movement suggest that the governments of all states include volunteering in national development plans as a component for achieving the goals of sustainable development [1].

For Ukraine, as well as for the whole world, volunteering is relevant and important. The Revolution of Dignity and the events caused by it in Ukraine led to significant changes in Ukrainian society. In particular, as a result of a number of factors, primarily the external aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, the territorial annexation and occupation of part of the Ukrainian territory, the inability of state structures to effectively respond to challenges and act in extreme conditions of social conflict was manifested. Which, in turn, forced the domestic civil society to demonstrate an impressive ability to consolidate and mobilize, to take upon itself the solution of the most acute and urgent problems.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The analysis of scientific research allows us to conclude that the experience of volunteer work both in Ukraine and abroad, in one form or another, is available in every country of the world. In many of them, it is legally fixed and has some features regarding the use of new approaches. The current state and peculiarities of the status of the volunteer movement

were studied by scientists from different countries, in particular: Bukhtiyarova I.G., Pastukh I.D., Strelchenko O.G., Serbyn R. A., Kornievsky O. A., Kharchenko S., Lyakh T. L., Gorelov D., Krapivina H. O., Bakovetska O. and many others. However, a comprehensive thorough study of all aspects of volunteering is an urgent issue for further research in this area.

Previously unsolved problems. The world community recognizes the volunteer movement as a way of preserving and strengthening universal human values, realizing the rights and responsibilities of citizens, personal growth through awareness of human potential.

The Universal Declaration of Volunteering states that volunteering is the foundation of civil society, bringing into people's lives the need for peace, freedom, security and justice. Voluntary activity, aimed at removing social stigma by supporting the most disadvantaged categories of the population, becomes important, especially in crisis periods of social life; ensuring a dignified existence of citizens who, due to objective circumstances, are unable to take care of themselves on their own; "filling" the shortcomings of the state social policy, primarily due to prompt response and the provision of effective targeted social assistance that meets the needs and requests of a specific person; spread of humanistic and altruistic ideas and attitudes in society, etc. The idea of social service, provision of free assistance to those who need it, active involvement of citizens in socially useful activities, in particular assistance to victims of natural disasters, environmental, industrial, humanitarian disasters, social, national, religious conflicts and confrontations, are perceived in developed countries as a completely ordinary phenomenon, therefore, the study of the volunteer movement both in Ukraine and throughout the world is relevant for the development of a democratic civil society.

The purpose of the article is a thorough study of the historical development, state and status of the volunteer movement in the world and in Ukraine.

Presentation of the main material. The volunteer movement is widely developed in the world and is considered as a global process of uniting people who seek to contribute to the improvement of their own and the global community's well-being. Volunteers are people of different ages and professions from various spheres and strata of society who give part of their strength, time, and knowledge for

the benefit of other people and society as a whole. World experience considers volunteering as a form of social work that can overcome the effect of people avoiding public problems, form a model of collective participation, reproduction of human values.

Speaking about volunteering, it should be noted that the definition of this phenomenon still needs a scientifically complete interpretation, taking into account all the multifaceted aspects. In the Soviet tradition, the term "volunteer", "volunteer" (from the Latin *voluntarius*, *voluntas* - good will) was perceived exclusively in the military context to denote a person who voluntarily entered military service. And only with the intensification of the world volunteer movement in its various forms in the last third of the 20th century, the spread in the post-Soviet space in the 1990s of the activities of numerous charitable organizations, 4 exchange programs, targeted charitable international programs, the term "volunteerism" was formalized and begins to be perceived as a type of socially useful activity, most often free and socially significant, provided by individuals - volunteers on a personal initiative or from a non-governmental non-commercial organization-association [5].

The emergence of the phenomenon of volunteerism is associated with the middle of the 19th century, and 1859 is considered the year of the emergence of the volunteer movement in the world. It was during this period that the famous French writer-journalist Jean-Henri Dunant proposed the creation of the Red Cross — an organization that would work on a volunteer basis and provide first aid to prisoners and wounded. Volunteer organizations around the world are still guided by the principles formulated by Henri Dunant. Some researchers single out the 20th century as the main milestone in the development of the volunteer movement. It was at this time that the first volunteer organizations were created [2; 3].

Voluntary activity gained special development in the USA, where this movement originated in the 19th century. It was during this period that the Civilian Conservation Corps was created as part of the New Deal policy to reduce unemployment and to carry out important work on the preservation of the environment and natural resources. The program gained extreme popularity among the population, becoming a prototype for a large number of mass, primarily ecologically oriented projects [4].

Since the 1990s, the volunteer movement in the USA has been gaining a mass character. It is

allowed to take part in it to different sections of the population, regardless of the level of education, income or profession. However, despite the voluntary nature, volunteering does not exclude responsibility for compliance with norms and requirements, preservation of material values, etc. Participation in the volunteer movement is a determining indicator of a person's personal qualities and characteristics (participation in voluntary aid projects is an absolute advantage when looking for a job; free help from highly qualified specialists, especially doctors or lawyers, provides them with reputation and popularity; volunteer experience significantly increases the chances of receiving scholarships for studies and admission to prestigious educational institutions; work as a volunteer is counted when determining work experience in the same way as paid work). It is also worth noting the support of the volunteer movement by state authorities in countries such as the USA, Canada, Australia, England, Italy, Japan and other developed countries, where it is believed that volunteering contributes to the support and strengthening of the basic principles of democracy, primarily because involves a large number of citizens in the decision-making process. The governments of these countries provide significant support to the volunteer movement, including through the adoption of legislative acts that stimulate its development, the creation of a system of state volunteer centers and special volunteer programs [5].

Among European countries, one of the highest rates of population participation in volunteering is observed in Great Britain — up to 30% and Ireland — 33%, and one of the most popular areas is social work, although in recent years the popularity of volunteering at sports events and in actions with preservation of the environment. In Great Britain, until the end of the 40s of the 20th century, the main medical and social services were provided by volunteer organizations, their activities supplemented the direct assistance of the family and the community [6].

The voluntary movement in the UK has strong support from the government, due to its recognition as an important element of social policy. This was especially noticeable in the 1980s, when the level of unemployment increased, and politicians, as well as society in general, began to consider volunteer work as a partial solution to this problem.

Volunteer work in Germany originated in 1788 thanks to the Hamburg Poor Code. In the

following decades, in most German settlements, the social protection of the poor was organized precisely thanks to volunteer work, which was institutionalized by the communal reform in Prussia in 1808. Thanks to volunteers, it became possible to provide social assistance with minimal use of public resources. Volunteer work often means more than providing support, and this raises issues of sufficient qualifications, competence and responsibility for the work. Therefore, organizations and groups of organizations develop different models of volunteer work that help people work for others [6].

Volunteerism in Germany is distinguished by its features, reflected in legislative initiatives, in particular: since 1964, the state program "Volunteer Social Year" (Freiwilliges Soziales Jahr (FSJ or Freiwilliges Ökologisches Jahr (further - FOJ)) has been implemented, which allows German youth to carry out practical activities during the year in social or environmental spheres; Since 2002, volunteering has been counted as an alternative to military service. FOJ is a full-time auxiliary practical activity for 6-12 months (with the possibility of extension to 18), which is carried out in hospitals; homes for the elderly; children's institutions; institutions for people with physical or mental disabilities.

The environmental component of FOJ includes voluntary work on farms, in forestry, museums, animal shelters, etc. Participation in such programs provides an opportunity to gain valuable life experience, decide on a future profession and is an integral component of successful community coexistence [7].

In France, about 20% of the adult population participates in voluntary initiatives on a permanent basis, volunteers are also involved in work in local authorities, public institutions, police and public security agencies, embassies and consulates. The most popular areas are projects in the fields of health care and rehabilitation, combating isolation and discrimination, adaptation of immigrants, educational and cultural projects [6].

In the Czech Republic, the activities of non-governmental organizations are accredited, which select and train volunteers, sign contracts with them and send them to work in organizations that need them. These can be both state bodies and territorial bodies of power and self-government [6].

In Hungary, the organizers of volunteer activities can be charitable organizations, state institutions, state or private service providers in the fields

of social assistance, culture, education and protection of minorities. Organizations that employ volunteers must register with the competent ministry. The Law of Hungary on Socially Beneficial Volunteering establishes a detailed bureaucratic registration procedure and the conditions under which registration may be refused [6].

In Italy, there are established principles and criteria that regulate relations between state institutions and volunteer organizations. Volunteers are given certain protection and rights, a number of obligations are established for volunteer organizations, in particular, mandatory health and third-party liability insurance. One of the largest volunteer organizations is the Italian Volunteer Foundation, created on the initiative of the Rome Savings Bank, which provides consulting and educational services to volunteers and volunteer organizations. He is also the founder of national awards to support the most promising and proactive volunteer groups that solve social problems. In Italy, there is also a Standing Committee of Heads of Volunteer Organizations and Foundations, which represents the interests of 2 million Italian volunteers before the government, parliament, church, and various public institutions [6].

Today, the Coordinating Committee of the International Voluntary Service (CCIVS) has been established under the auspices of UNESCO with headquarters in Paris [2; 3].

The main innovative means of activity of international volunteer associations are [8]:

— Alliance of European Voluntary Service, Association of Voluntary Service, Coordinating Committee for International Voluntary Service coordinate the activities of European national volunteer organizations, short-term and long-term volunteer work camps, promoting the ideas of international cooperation, peace and mutual understanding and the interests of volunteering at the level of governments and social institutions;

— The International Christian Youth Exchange Federation implements the ideas of global education and intercultural education of children, the elderly and the disabled, organizes children's centers and implements environmental projects;

— The international volunteer organization Service Civil International promotes the ideas of peace, international understanding and solidarity, social justice and environmental protection in the form of volunteer anti-war projects, pacifist seminars and trainings [8];

— International volunteer associations United Nations Volunteers — an organization directly subordinated to the UN, engaged in supporting sustainable global development on the planet by promoting the ideas of volunteerism and mobilizing volunteers to solve specific practical tasks of providing assistance to refugees, HIV-infected, disabled children; in the field of child and adult education, health care, urban development, suffrage and voter rights protection, gender equality and women's rights, etc., in almost all UN member countries [8];

— The international youth organization Youth Action for Peace promotes ideas of peace and cooperation between countries and actively opposes military conflicts, organizes volunteer anti-war projects, pacifist seminars and trainings, develops methods of non-violent resolution of military conflicts, work with refugees, socially vulnerable groups, lobbying of anti-war and peace-making ideas among political parties and organizations [8];

— The Christian Children's Fund promotes the improvement of the situation of children and youth in the world by developing and implementing programs, providing social services, training specialists and volunteers of social work, developing international cooperation in partnership with state and non-state structures [8];

— The Ukrainian Association of Social Educators and Social Work Specialists is an independent, charitable public organization whose activities are carried out on the basis of the development of social initiatives, self-government, openness, voluntary membership and participation in its affairs. The main tasks of the Association are the consolidation of efforts in the formation and development of social pedagogy and social work in Ukraine; support of interested organizations and individuals in the improvement of social and economic living conditions, in the development of people's creative potential, the formation of a personality that can act independently, proactively, responsibly; organization of activities of social pedagogues and specialists in providing assistance to citizens and groups who have difficulties in socialization, adaptation and social rehabilitation; promotion of raising the professional level and establishment of the social status of social teachers and social workers, protection of their professional interests, creation of favorable working conditions, implementation of control over the implementation of ethical standards. Since 1994, he has been a full

member of the International Federation of Social Workers [8];

— Ukrainian Foundation "Welfare of Children", which uses the national and international potential of the community to provide various social services to people who need help;

— Community Service Volunteers (UK) provides young people aged 16 to 35 with opportunities to volunteer in areas such as social work, education, environmental protection, media and volunteer innovation;

— The National Association of Volunteer Bureaux (Great Britain), which is called the "volunteer labor exchange", acts as a network of contact bureaus for people who want to work voluntarily; the main task of volunteer agencies is consultation, training and management of people in the organization where their help is needed [8].

In addition, it was and is extremely important to train representatives of organizations to manage the activities of volunteers, as this is one of the main problems that prevent the public from engaging in cooperation. The internal political crisis that led to the imbalance of the state administration system, the lack of quality management solutions, the lack of resource opportunities, and external aggression, which deepened the imbalance between the state's ability to effectively perform its functions and provide for the basic needs of citizens, led to the growth of the activity of the volunteer movement [7].

Since the state structures are not always able to respond to all the requests of the society, the domestic civil society is forced to take on the challenge, in which it demonstrates an impressive ability to consolidate and mobilize, having managed to create an effective network of public initiatives and associations that have taken on the solution the most acute and urgent problems. Public and volunteer movement is gaining special importance. Volunteer activity has acquired all the signs of the most effective form of self-organization of the population. Flexible forms of volunteering have proven to be the most productive in practice, as bypassing bureaucratic procedures in extraordinary circumstances saves time and ultimately saves lives.

In the midst of socio-economic and political instability, we should also note the comprehensive support of voluntary activity of Ukrainian citizens, the consolidation of this trend as an integral component of social life [5].

Summarizing the results of the analysis of foreign studies, we must admit that the theory and practice of volunteer work in foreign countries have a higher official status and greater practical experience than in Ukraine. Volunteer activity is relevant and important for the whole world, because the volunteer movement is a way of preserving and strengthening universal human values, realizing the rights and responsibilities of citizens, and personal growth through realizing human potential. However, it should be noted that each country must find its own model of volunteer activity regulation, based on its social, cultural and economic conditions, an important component of which should still be a clear

and effective interaction of the public with the authorities in order to obtain a synergistic effect of their activities.

It should be noted that the volunteer work of foreign countries, aimed at improving the welfare of society, has its own directions and forms of work, which are expedient to practically implement in our country. Of course, not all of their findings can be applied in our country due to significant differences, in particular at the socio-economic level. At the same time, mutual enrichment with ideas and experience of organizing volunteer work is an important factor in its development in Ukraine.

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